

An advanced application for learning robotics using Augmented Reality

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Abstract

Robotics is a multidisciplinary branch of engineering that nowadays presents many challenges to overcome for having a greater presence and impact in our society. Due to its characteristics, usually it is investigated by the integration that it can have with other technologies and one of these is augmented reality (AR), which consists of combining the real and virtual world through computer processes, improving the visual experience and the scientific application. The main objective of this project is to develop an application that implements AR for the visual projection and supervision of robots, where the solution is based on a client-server architecture. The server is responsible for controlling the robot using ROS (*Robotics Operative System*), and the client is based on a platform compatible with Unity that includes the AR Vuforia engine, including the characteristics of graphic, physical and AR simulation of the robot to be controlled. To bring about this investigation it was used a configured Windows 10 environment with WSL (*Windows Subsystem Linux*), allowing ROS and Unity to coexist on the same machine, meanwhile, to overcome the communication challenge that exists between them, it used the solution proposed by the Unity Robotics Hub project. This software permits to add three robot models with distinctive characteristics to recreate some use cases with AR. Finally, it is possible to obtain an independent Unity client based on UWP (*Universal Windows Platform*) oriented to desktops and with AR functionalities.

Keywords: Robotics; Augmented reality; Robotic Operative System (ROS); Unity, Vuforia, Ros #, Unity Robotics Hub.

1 Introduction

Robotics is a multidisciplinary branch of engineering that currently presents many challenges to overcome in order to have a greater presence and impact in our society. The research drives the current state of this branch with new improvements that are always being sought by collaborating with technologies from other environments to enhance current robotic solutions and one of them is augmented reality (AR).

Augmented reality (AR) is a variation of Virtual Reality (VR), where the user can see in the same environment how real objects and the superimposition of virtual objects coexist (Azuma, 1997). This offers the improvement of our perception by helping us to see, hear and feel our environment in new ways (Krevelen, 2007). The AR potential can be used in multiple areas and it also helps to improve interaction difficulties in current challenges. Some examples about this application cases are:

- In an industrial manufacturing environment, the management of a production line can be supported by visual indicators to know some parameters such as the state of operation, quality control of the products, alerts that include the location of a possible failure in any component of the line.
- In the field of medicine, doctors can speed up the process of diagnosing a physical injury in a patient while obtaining real-time visual feedback from a virtual projection over the affected area with the respective bones in that area.
- For entertainment, focusing on video games, the user experience can be enhanced by including features that use real physical effects in conjunction with the 2D/3D elements of the video game itself.
- For educative environment, simulations is a commonly tool to avoid some executions of experiments because doing them with real equipment and components can be significant expensive, so this is where AR offers an improvement in the student experience that can observe a better physical interaction between two virtual 3D elements in an already existing and easy to manage real environment.

In the field of applications of AR its notable the intention of integration with robotics, which offer the enhancement of existing solutions in multiple areas and the experimental research. Currently there are already several investigations that study these characteristics:

- Improve the navigation control of mobile robots using head mounted displays (HMDs) and AR (Kästner & Lambrecht, 2019). In this case tests were carried out using a pair of Microsoft HoloLens that allow the user to indicate the displacement positions of the robot with hand gestures, these are transmitted to the robot's operating system to be processed and executed, in addition to giving user trajectory planning feedback.
- Facilitate the teleoperation of aerial robots (Hedayati, Walker, & Szafir, 2019). In this case they used a commercial drone and a pair of Microsoft HoloLens, where a user get this equipment and obtained details feedback about robot vision with other perspectives that helped flight operation.
- Improve trajectory planning with AR-based interfaces (Fang, Ong, & Nee, 2013). The authors exposed some of the difficulties of human-machine interaction, making a specific focus on industrial robots and how these can be very limited to the use of the programming languages of each manufacturer, especially in relation to trajectory planning, but through AR they managed to develop an interface oriented to the use of a cubic marker that allows managing the points of the desired trajectory. Two aspects of this development can be highlighted: first, the use of the cubic marker that has several targets associated with it, so that when it is identified by the camera, it executes an action on the indicated point, and the use of a method based on Euclidean distance to resolve and assist to the user during point generation.
- Planning and simulation of a robotic cell using AR (Pai, Yap, & Singh, 2014), in this research the authors use some technologies to find alternatives in the planning process of a future robotic cell installation, offering a cost reduction and increased efficiencies that are representative for small and medium-sized businesses. The cell that they recreate to simulate the manufacturing plant environment is made up of a robotic arm, a conveyor belt, a pallet and a numerical control machine (CNC), with the aim of recreating material handling processes. An interesting point that should not be overlooked are the technologies that were used, such as a HMD as vision equipment and an interface based on C++ with OpenGL through ARToolKit to generate the virtual elements, as well as a target for everything related to the interaction of the user.
- Teleoperation of a manipulator-type industrial robot based on AR (Solanes, et al., 2020), this paper seeks a considerable improvement in the teleoperation of this type of robots, which are common in manufacturing areas and for this reason makes it relevant to improve their management. Regarding the hardware, they use a game controller (gamepad) and a HMD which receive the feedback from the control carried out on a robotic arm. For the development of the interface, they use Unity and Visual Studio on Windows 10, managing to generate an application for the HMD with the MixedRealityToolkit in Unity. The results showed the benefits of a control feedback to enhance the user experience.

2 Software architecture

In this research we used some technologies such as 3D objects render, robotics controls, AR and communications between software components. Some of these technologies don't have any compatibilities between them therefore it was a huge challenge to resolve as real time communication.

2.1 Technologies and tooling

- OS Windows 10 – Enterprise Edition
- Ubuntu 18.04 LTS over WSL (Window Subsystem Linux), specifically WSL 2 in W10
- ROS (Robotic Operative System) Melodic, corresponding version in Ubuntu 18.04
- MoveIt, open-source framework for controlling robots in ROS
- Robot's models in URDF (Universal Robot Description Format); UR3, HOAP3 and Shadow Hand (Figure 1)
- Unity, a world class game engine

- Visual Studio 2019 or latest
- Vuforia, AR engine
- Unity Robotics Hub, library for communicate ROS and Unity, predecessor of RosSharp project
- UWP (Universal Windows Platform), target platform for client out Unity environment
- Webcam (1920 x 1080p, 30 fps)

Figure 1. Real robots model used in this project: (Universal Robots, 2021; Galdeano, Chemori, Krut, & Fraise, 2014; Galdeano, Chemori, Krut, & Fraise, 2014)

2.2 Integration

In design process the best software architecture for this solution has a client-server approach, therefore the classification for each component was grouped in infrastructure, server, client and communication components (Figure 2):

- *Infrastructure*: based in W10 OS and extra layer with WSL 2
- *Server*: which has the responsibility to process all robot movements and calculate trajectories with MoveIt in ROS (programmed in Python). This layer run over Ubuntu 18 in WSL into the same machine
- *Client*: who has the AR features and 3D renders in Unity combined with Vuforia engine in the develop environment; in production case all this client runs in UWP. All logics for this layer was coding in C#
- *Communication*: to resolve the interaction between client and server was necessary to use libraries from Unity Robotics Hub, allowing the communication with TCP socket in real time and low latency.

Figure 2. Architecture solution with all key components

The default robotics models are in URDF, this format is ROS oriented but can be transformed with a package from Unity Robotics Hub called *URDF Imported* which generate a robot model into the Unity scene with all visual and physics properties, including the joints as articulation bodies allowing an easier control. Another key

library in this solution is *ROS TCP Connector* for client side in Unity and *ROS RCP Endpoint* for ROS server side, both are from Unity Robotics Hub and allow the communication.

3 Experiments

There were designed three experiments with the aim of testing the previous environment. Attempt to recreate real life process with some popular robotics model and all cases the logic structure is the same both on the client and on the server (Figure 3).

For AR features, Vuforia engine has many ways to detect and render the Unity model in real time video from camera device. The selected way was focused on detect targets features mainly with *VuMark* (a special image with high contrast and optimized to be detected) and the render action succeed when the camera's scan detected the established target in the real environment.

On the client side the general execution process renders the robotic model when a trigger is activated because the camera's scan detects a target on real environment, after this the robot is ready to go to the next state (movement combination), when pressing the respective button, the actual state and next state data is sent to the server endpoint. On the other hand, the server waits for client request, once it has arrived the request data about robot state (robot's joints and next request state) redirect this data to mover service which processes it with a robots model previously charged in a *MoveIt* node (with all movement restriction and config to calculate trajectories), if the next state doesn't have collisions or trajectories errors, this service generates an output with the new position coordinates and return them to the client. Finally, the client executes the movements in visual model until robot has the final state.

Figure 3. Software components, modules and relationships in client and server

3.1 Pick and place with a robotic arm

A typically pick and place process was designed with a robotic arm UR3 from Universal Robots and pneumatic vacuum suction cup in the extreme of the robot arm. This experiment has 4 states or positions and just one trigger. Where robot begins its initial state, it picks a box up, moves it to the opposite direction and places it in the green zone (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Pick and place process with UR3 and target

3.2 Robotic humanoid control

The control for humanoid robot is complex, but an adjustment was made to remain the torso fixed at a certain coordinate. It allowed to use the robot HOAP3 from Fujitsu. This experiment has 3 independently states associated to each body part and each one has its trigger, when all triggers are executed, the robot copies an equilibrium position on one foot (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Robotic humanoid control with HOAP3

3.3 Grasping with robotic hand

Shadow Hand form Shadow Robot was selected to realize the grasping activity. This experiment has 2 independently states, pre-grasp and post-grasp, when all stages were completed, the robot catches the cylinder from its initial position to another final opposite position (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Grasping process with Shadow Hand

3.4 Client app in UWP

Unity is mainly used for development stage, but it can compile to target device when the app will be executed, in this case the limitation is about Vuforia engine compatibility, this one only works with mobile devices (Android, iOS) and UWP, but the research scope is about the development in the same machine, therefore UWP was selected as production target, because it allows to execute the app in desktop with W10.

To improve the user experience, a main menu was included in the app, which groups all the experiments in AR and virtual version (Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Main menu for all experiment in UWP

Figure 7. Scene pick and place with robotic arm without AR

4 Benefits in the learning process

It is worth pointing that this research also has some positive insights for learning process focussed on robotics students or similar in related areas, this is the case for the degree in Robotics and the master's degree in Automatic and Robotic students in University of Alicante.

The technologies and techniques tested here could be used for designing some new experiments in laboratories or interesting workshop, being able to have the following advantages:

- Configuring the develop environment with only one personal laptop or desktop, because these experiments use ROS in WSL as backend and Unity in W10 as client both in the same instance
- Learning about robotics physics with robot models in Unity, this allows to test some full featured models in an easy way with URDF file from real models
- Practicing the control algorithms over robots with ROS and planning trajectories with MoveIt framework
- Improving technical skills in programming languages as C# in Unity and Python or C++ in ROS
- Demonstrate a way to build new robotics products with AR, due to is possible generate a standalone apps with external and enterprise grade frameworks

5 Conclusions

After performing the iterations and preparing the development environment for this research, the conclusions would be the followings:

- The AR development environment for using W10 as S.O. base to support Unity and WSL, the latter allows the use of Ubuntu distribution with a ROS respective version, which is a viable alternative to avoid virtual machines by third parties in Windows, due to its easy configuration and compatibility with graphics recourses
- Unity and Vuforia are good options to develop interfaces with AR, both are allowed to do a project with three use cases with different based robotic models: UR3, HOAP3 and Shadow Hand. The iterations and the proof of concept had generated many scenes with and without AR in a modular way. It is worth mentioning the power of Unity to export multitarget clients. In this research was generated an UWP app which is ready for production environment, doesn't need Unity installation in destiny device and it is easy to distribute
- The communication between a ROS node or server with an app client based in Unity is not native but exist some solutions to mitigate this complexity. The projects in Unity Robotics Hub were a key component as well as it integrates a two-ways communication and uses ROS's message scheme to generate standard or custom messages
- The communication components and the architecture for this application allowed the response with information state and the coordinates to the client (with a previous services validation with MoveIt) then the client was independently getting this data and executing the movement with scene and physical restriction in Unity (all workload belongs to client side)
- Around benefits in learning process, this research has many resources to build practices in laboratories or make some workshops about robotics and AR, where students can learn more about these topics with practical examples and reinforce other knowledge areas which as: programming languages, algorithms, networks, 3D modeling and some others.

In future researches and projects will be interesting to consider other topics as: limitations of Articulation Body components in Unity, improvement of the AR experience with better hardware features, to make tests and integrations with mobiles devices and to use container technologies as Docker for development and deploy ROS nodes.

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